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Research Article

THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN CAFFEINE CONSUMPTION AND SLEEPING HABITS AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Objectives: To measure the daily caffeine intake among the medical students, to determine the relation between caffeine and sleeping habits, and to approximate the amount of caffeine that can affect sleep.

Methods: Study design is cross-sectional study, it will be conducted in King Saud University – Collage of Medicine (male students), on 108 subjects, using stratified random sampling and self-administered questionnaire, and for the data analysis we will use SPSS statistics software.

Results: 1) The highest portion of the sample at (38.6%) are the moderate level caffeine consumers, (36.6%) are the low-level caffeine consumers, and there are 11.9% who consume caffeine highly, and 12.9% who don't consume.

2) The highest portion of subjects not using caffeine beverages was (inability to sleep while drinking it) with a percentage of (5.9%).

3) The sleeping quality was affected most in high caffeine intake group.

4) There is relation with a statistical significance between high caffeine consumption and sleeping quality.

5) Results showed that 50% of smokers experienced poor sleep quality, where in non-smokers, the prevalence was 26.4%.

6) Results showed that 34.1% of non-physically active subjects experienced poor sleep quality, where in physically active ones, the prevalence was 26.7%.

Conclusion: In this study, caffeine consumption and sleep habits were analyzed among medical students and showed that medical students whom consumed high amounts of caffeine, faced problems falling asleep and struggle with poor sleep quality.

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INTRODUCTION:

Caffeine, 3,5,7-trimethylxanthine, is a stimulant of the central nervous system (CNS)(1); daily consumed by a large population in the form of coffee, tea or cola drinks. Although insomnia has been included as one major symptom of both acute and chronic caffeine intoxication, there are few quantified studies of sleep after moderate doses. Caffeine enters the bloodstream through the stomach and small intestine and can have a stimulating effect as soon as 15 minutes after it is consumed. Once in the body, caffeine will persist for several hours: it takes about 6 hours for one half of the caffeine to be eliminated (2).

Caffeine consumption is a prevalent phenomenon in modern society, and this has been a field of interest studied by many health organizations. But unfortunately, no body has narrowed the scope on its effect on medical students. Hence, their life style imposes on them to have a frequent encounter with this substance. In review of previous studies and literature a suggestion arise that there is a causal relationship between a negative effects of caffeine consumption on sleep patterns among adolescents (3). In comparison with our study, we aim to focus specifically on medical students.

In general, studying the consumption of caffeine solution is a prevalent problem worldwide, and this has relevance with medical student who consume large volumes of caffeine to maintain a high level of concentration and focus during intensive studies. From this point, we aim to study how this correlates to sleeping habits to have a healthy generation of doctors, so addressing their potential matter is crucial. After acknowledging the problem, we want to contribute to the medical student's community by pointing out the risk factors (caffeine) that affect sleeping habits and how to prevent them, in a simple comprehensive language that will be useful to them. Our objectives are to measure the caffeine intake among the medical students and to determine the relation between caffeine and sleeping habits. So, this study was aimed to answer the following question (What is the effect of Caffeine intake on sleeping pattern among the medical students?). We hypothesized that more than 50% of medical students consume daily caffeine, and about 30% of sleeping habits are disturbed by caffeine consumption. Completing this study will give us a clear overview of the prevalence of caffeine solution intake among medical students. We will deliver our results to most of the medical students and faculty members in simple understandable language, to raise the awareness of this particular issue. Knowing the risk factors and how to prevent them will provide solutions to those who are consuming caffeine solution in large volumes. We want

to help the medical student community, making it more aware and a productive community, through introducing the concepts of moderate caffeine consumption, changing in lifestyles, and avoiding risk factors. Our sample is focused on medical students, who will spread the word to their families and friends to achieve a good degree of awareness in our society.

METHODS:

A quantitative cross-sectional study was conducted in King Saud University – Collage of Medicine 2014-2015. Our research was done on caffeine intake and its association with sleeping habits among male students of KSU medical collage. The subjects in this study were male medical students. Including criteria were 1st, 2nd and 3rd year male medical students with excluding 4th and 5th year male medical students. This is based on the availability and the easy access to the subjects. Our sample size was calculated by the following equation:

$$N = \frac{(1.96+0.842)^2((62.9*1-62.9)+(37.1*1-37.1))}{(62.9+37.1)^2} = 108$$

(N) Which is the sample size, ($Z\alpha = 1.96$) for 95% confidence level, ($Z\beta = 0.842$) at 80% power, ($p1 = 62.9\%$) is the proportion of bad sleeping habits among heavy caffeine consumers, ($p2 = 37.1\%$) is the proportion of bad sleeping habits among normal caffeine consumers, ($q1$) is $(100-p1)$ and ($q2$) is $(100-p2)$. Students were selected by stratified random sampling. We collected 18 students from each group in each year. The data was collected through self-administered questionnaires that were distributed among the subjects. The questionnaire included 30 questions, which were categorized into questions assessing caffeine intake, and sleeping habits. Questionnaire included sleeping questions was taken from The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (4), scoring 5 or less for good sleep and 5 or more for poor sleep. The one assessing caffeine intake was from International Coffee Organization (5), which is based on the following classification:

- Low caffeine users: less than 200mg per day
- Moderate caffeine users: 200-400mg per day
- High caffeine users: more than 400mg per day

The pilot study was conducted on 11 person. The questionnaire was in English language, which included eclectic data such as age, smoking, physical activity, caffeine intake and sleeping habits. Statistical analysis was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Statistic techniques used were Frequencies and percentages for identifying the characteristics of individuals, and the consumption percentage of caffeine and sleeping habits, Chi-square test to identify the association between caffeine consumption and sleeping habits, assumed there was a statistically significance when P-value less than 0.05. Ethical Consideration was in an informed consent, distinct and obvious to the participants and implied the

goal of the study; also they had the right to disengage when they want to without any penalties toward the study team.

This study is designed for the first time during the CMED 305 curriculum time from September 2014, also not funded by any organization, there are no conflicts of interest present, we will clarify to the participant that this study is not likely to benefit the participant immediately.

RESULTS:

First: results related to primary data:

The relationship between smoking and sleeping:

Table no. (1)

Sample distribution according to quality of sleep

Table no. (1) shows that there is no statistical significance between sleep and smoking, the table shows that Chi-Square value was (3.207), with p-value of (0.073). According to the previous result there is no association between sleep and smoking in this study's sample size. Even though there was no statistical significance between smoking and sleeping, the non-smokers tend to have better sleep than the smokers. The results were (50%) of smokers have good sleep while non-smokers were (73.6%)

The relationship between exercising and sleeping:

Table no. (2)

Sample distribution according to quality of sleep

Table no. (2) shows that there is no statistical significance between sleep and exercising, where Chi-Square value was (0.653) with a p-value of (0.419). The results show no association between exercise and sleep. Even though there were no association between the two, those who exercise have better sleep quality than those who do not exercise, because the result for those who exercise was (73.3%), and a (65.9%) for those who do not exercise.

Second: Results and percentages related to caffeine consumption:

Table No. (3)

Sample distribution according to the consumption of caffeine by students

Table no. (3) shows that the biggest amount of sample (39) 38.6% have moderate caffeine intake, (37) 36.6% consume low amounts of caffeine, and (12) 11.9% have high caffeine intake; while there are (13) 12.9% not consuming caffeine.

If no caffeinated beverages, why not?

Table no. (4)

Causes of not consuming caffeine beverages

Table no. (4) shows sample distribution according to causes of not consuming caffeine beverages, whereas there are (6) 5.9% not consuming caffeine beverages as they can not sleep after drinking, but there are (5) 5.0% not consuming caffeine as they don't like the taste of caffeinated beverages, there are (2) 2.0% do not consume caffeine for health reasons.

Would you characterize your drinking caffeinated beverages as a habit, addiction, or neither?

Table no. (5)

Sample distribution according to the characteristics of drinking caffeine beverages (Habit, addiction or neither) Table no. (5) shows that the biggest amount of sample (47) 46.5% consider caffeine consumption a habit, but (27) 26.7% consider caffeine consumption neither addiction nor habit, lastly, (14) 13.9% consider themselves as addicted.

After being aware of the many side effects of abusing caffeine, such as anxiety, insomnia, headache, tremors, poor concentration, etc., would you still drink as much?

Table no. (6)

Table no. (6) shows the biggest amount of sample (53) 52.5% will proceed drinking caffeinated beverage disregarding the obvious side effects, but there are (35) 34.6% will consume caffeine cautiously regarding the side effects.

Third: results related to sleeping habits: -

How long (in minutes) has it taken you to fall asleep each night?

Table no. (7)

Sample distribution according to time taken you to fall asleep each night

Table no. (7) shows sample distribution according to how much time you take to fall asleep each night, as the biggest amount of sample (49) 48.5% takes less than 16 minutes to fall asleep, (39) 38.6% take 16-30 minutes to fall asleep, as there are (11) 10.9% take 31-60 minutes to fall asleep, whereas there are (11) 10.9% take more than 60 minutes.

How many hours of actual sleep do you get at night?

Table no. (8)

Sample distribution according to sleeping hours

Table no. (8) shows an average of sleeping hours of sample size which is (5.9) hours, (31) 30.7% are sleeping (7) hours or more, as there are (28) 27.7% who sleep (6) hours, whereas (25) 24.8% take (5) hours, and the last (17) 16.8% sleep less than 5 hours.

Sleep quality:

Table no. (9)

Sample distribution according to sleeping quality
Table no. (9) shows sample distribution according to quality of sleep, as there are (71) 70.3% have good sleep quality, as there are (30) 29.7% have poor sleep quality.

Fourth: relationship between caffeine consumption and sleeping:

Table no. (10) & Figure no. (1,2)

Sample distribution according to quality of sleep

Chi-Square: 15.245 p-value: 0.002

Table no. (10) shows that there is a statistical significance between caffeine consumption and the quality of sleep, as Chi-Square value is 15.245, with a p-value of 0.002, which means that there is a difference in the quality of sleep between those who drink caffeinated beverages excessively from the other groups (moderate, low, and no caffeine intake).

Results of Table (10), Figure (1) showed that individuals with higher (good) sleep quality, 29 of them with 40.8% are consuming caffeine in low amounts, (25) (35.2%) are consuming caffeine moderately. (10) 14.1% are not using caffeine, lastly, there are (7) (9.9 %) consume caffeine excessively.

Results of Table (10), Figure (2) showed that individuals with poor sleep quality, 14 of them with 46.7% are consuming caffeine excessively, (8) 26.7% are consuming caffeine on moderate manner. (5) (16.7%) drink low amounts of caffeine, lastly, there are (3) (10.0%) not consuming caffeine.

DISCUSSION:

The study shows that the largest portion of the sample 86.1% are non smokers, but 13.9% are smokers which runs in parallel with a study previously conducted among medical students at King Saud University that suggest about the same prevalence (6) including such criteria in this study to test it's effect in conjunction with caffeine consumption in altering sleep negatively as other studies implied (7). In correlation with this study, results showed that 50% of smokers experienced poor sleep quality, where in non-smokers, the prevalence was 26.4%.

In opposition to having a personal habit that has a negative impact on sleeping patterns the study added to it's interests the physical vitality of the participants as a

variable and it showed that 59.4% of the sample exercise and 40.6% don't, as other studies suggest that exercising promotes better quality of sleep (8). In correlation with this study, results showed that 34.1% of non-physically active subjects experienced poor sleep quality, where in physically active ones, the prevalence was 26.7%.

It was noticed that 87.1% of the sample were caffeine consumers, among them 11.9% of high caffeine intake, which is the group that holds the hallmark of the study, which correlates with what was previously published, in a 2012 study assessed the impact on sleep of caffeine consumption at different times of day, suggesting that caffeine consumed up to six hours before sleep may have disruptive effects on sleep (9).

Researchers also found that among the adult population, consuming caffeine before sleep resulted in increased sleep onset time, reduced total sleep time, and poorer sleep quality. Studies have shown that adolescents consume more caffeine later in the week, which correlates with shorter total sleep time and decreased sleep quality (10). Which is the same incidental finding in this study at 46.7% of the high caffeine intake group who reported poor sleeping quality.

CONCLUSION / RECOMMENDATIONS:

In this study, caffeine consumption and sleep habits were analyzed among medical students.

The study showed that medical students whom consumed high amounts of caffeine, faced problems falling a sleep and struggle with poor sleep quality.

The current study focused on caffeine beverages but did not investigate the effect of energy supplements as: energy bars, herbal boosters, medications containing high level of caffeine, and caffeinated food. Which proved to play a major role in other study and is recommended to include such variable in future studies.

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Tables & Graphs:

(Tables)

- **First: results related to primary data:**
The relationship between smoking and sleeping:

Table no. (1):Sample distribution according to quality of sleep for (smokers and non-smokers)

Smoking		Sleep quality		Total
		Good sleep quality	Poor sleep quality	
Yes	F	7	7	14
	%	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
no	F	64	23	87
	%	73.6%	26.4%	100.0%
Total	F	71	30	101
	%	70.3%	29.7%	100.0%

The relationship between exercising and sleeping:**Table no. (2):**Sample distribution according to quality of sleep for (Exercising)

Exercise/activity		Sleep quality		Total
		Good sleep quality	Poor sleep quality	
yes	F	44	16	60
	%	73.3%	26.7%	100.0%
no	F	27	14	41
	%	65.9%	34.1%	100.0%
Total	F	71	30	101
	%	70.3%	29.7%	100.0%

- **Second: Results and percentages related to caffeine consumption by students:**

Table No. (3):Sample distribution according to consuming of caffeine by students

	Frequency	Percent
No caffeine	13	12.9
Low caffeine users	37	36.6
Moderate caffeine users	39	38.6
High caffeine users	12	11.9
Total	101	100.0

Table no. (4) :Causes of not consuming caffeine beverages

	Frequency	Percent
I don't like the taste of caffeinated beverages	5	5.0
I do not drink caffeinated beverages for health reasons	2	2.0
I can't sleep when drinking caffeinated beverages	6	5.9
Caffeine users	88	87.1
Total	101	100.0

Table no. (5):Sample distribution according to the characteristics of drinking caffeine beverages, (habit, addiction, or neither)

	Frequency	Percent
Habit	47	46.5
Addiction	14	13.9
Neither	27	26.7
NOT Caffeine users	13	12.9
Total	101	100.0

Table no. (6):Sample distribution according to the subject's continuity on caffeine even with their knowledge of its many side effects

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	53	52.5
No	35	34.6
Total	89	88.1
NOT Caffeine users	13	12.9
Total	101	100.0

- Third: results related to sleeping habits: -

Table no. (7): Sample distribution according to time taken to initiate sleep each night

	Frequency	Percent
Less than 16 minutes	49	48.5
16 - 30 minutes	39	38.6
31-60 minutes	11	10.9
More than 60 minutes	2	2.0
Total	101	100.0

Table no. (8):Sample distribution according to sleeping hours

	Frequency	Percent
7 hours or more	31	30.7
6 hours	28	27.7
5 hours	25	24.8
Less than 5 hours	17	16.8
Total	101	100.0

Table no. (9): Sample distribution according to quality of sleep

	Frequency	Percent
Good sleep quality	71	70.3
Poor sleep quality	30	29.7
Total	101	100.0

- **Fourth: relationship between caffeine consumption and sleeping quality:**

Table no. (10) : Sample distribution according to quality of sleep

Sleep quality		Caffeine consumption				Total
		No caffeine	Low caffeine users	Moderate caffeine users	High caffeine users	
Good sleep quality	F	10	29	25	7	71
	%	14.1%	40.8%	35.2%	9.9%	100.0%
Poor sleep quality	F	3	5	8	14	30
	%	10.0%	16.7%	26.7%	46.7%	100.0%
Total	F	13	37	39	12	101
	%	12.9%	36.6%	38.6%	11.9%	100.0%

(Figures)

Figure no. (1,2)
Sample distribution according to sleeping quality

